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**TYOLOGY OF TASKS FOR THE USE OF VOCABULARY IN
DIFFERENT TYPES OF SPEECH ACTIVITY**

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Abstract. this article provides information about typology of tasks for the use of lexical resources in different situations. In addition, it gives brief notions about speech activity and ideas from famous pedagogues who contributed in the sphere of pedagogy.

Keywords: *communicative, monologue, speech, game, spontaneity, speech task.*

This stage involves the use of learned vocabulary in independent statements, in new conditions. Speech abilities are manifested here in a new quality - in the form of skills. Skills are based on knowledge of lexical units and the rules of their use, as well as on the operation of these units, brought to automatism. One of the main characteristics of the skill is its stability in changing situations, dynamism.

Interaction in educational conditions only becomes truly communicative when the speaker chooses what to say and how to do it [1]. On the way to communicative interaction, there are stages of controlled, prepared and unprepared speech.

At the first stage, the teacher's role in preparing for the utterance is great: he determines the form (means of expression) and the content of the utterance. Tasks at this stage have a lot in common with transformational exercises, for example: "retell the dialogue in a monologue form based on keywords, adding details and your own assessments".

Prepared speech presupposes a certain freedom either in choosing the means of expressing thoughts, or in determining the content of the statement: "put questions to the watched film and prepare answers to them", "expand theses into a statement on a certain topic", "give examples of statements with these words and phrases, describe the relevant situations".

The highest level of development of speech abilities is independence both in the choice of form and content.

The best conditions for the creative application of acquired knowledge and skills, in our opinion, are created in communicative games and when discussing problematic situations.

Communicative games can be used at all stages of the formation of speech skills - from controlled to unprepared speech - provided that appropriate goals are set and, for example, appropriate design of role-playing cards in role-playing games.

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Communicative games provide the opportunity for real communication, albeit within artificially defined boundaries. There are 8 spheres of oral communication, according to which it is necessary to form speech skills:

- service (social and communicative roles of the buyer, passenger, patient, subscriber, canteen visitor, and so on);
- family (social and communicative roles of father, mother, son, daughter, and so on);
- professional and labor (roles of manager, subordinate, student, colleague, employee, and so on);
- socio-cultural (roles of an acquaintance, friend, traveling companion, and so on);
- social activities (roles of a member of a public organization, correspondent, and so on);
- administrative and legal (roles of a visitor to a state institution, applicant, plaintiff, and so on);
- games and hobbies (roles of a collector, gardener, fisherman, animal lover and so on);
- entertainment and mass work (spectator in the theater, circus, TV viewer, and so on) [2].

When teaching in real communication situations, role-playing and business games can be used.

The peculiarity of the game in high school age is the focus on self-affirmation, humorous coloring, the desire to draw, orientation to speech activity [3].

In a role-playing game, the student gets a certain role and must behave in accordance with it. A role-playing game is a type of group educational activity aimed at conditional reproduction by participants of real practical activities of people based on role cards or a script. A description of the role can be given in a role card, while it is possible to present detailed information: information about a person (kind, honest, lazy, and so on), about his life and speech experience, habits, hobbies, and the like is given. However, the information should not be presented in too much detail, since in this case the participant of the game loses the opportunity to show creativity [4]. The description can also be brief so that the student can imagine the image of the character whose role he will play. Thus, each participant of the role-playing game performs speech actions due to the communication situation, but each of them has a certain freedom of action, speech actions.

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Role-playing game carries an element of surprise, spontaneity and involves spontaneous reaction. It is the element of surprise and unpreparedness, the unpredictability of the situation, its provoking nature that engages in interactive interaction in a foreign language. A mandatory element of games is the resolution of a problematic situation. A role-playing game based on solving a problem ensures maximum activation of students' communicative activity.

Role-playing involves the conscious and voluntary performance of a role and its subsequent discussion in a group.

When using business games, the student can express his own thoughts, so to speak, play himself in given game conditions, in a certain situation that simulates the real one. The educational business game provides a more complete mastery of a foreign language as a means of professional communication. The business game has individual features inherent only in this type of educational work, without which the game cannot be considered business: modeling in the game close to real conditions of professional activity; the presence of conflict situations; mandatory joint activity of the participants of the game. The preparatory stage of this form of work in the classroom is to determine the main areas of professional interests of students as future specialists.

One of the advantages of the business game is the principle of the two-dimensional nature of the game educational activity. On the one hand, a business game solves "serious" tasks for the development of a specialist's personality, trainees master the skills of interaction in a work team, skills of professional communication and people management. On the other hand, this activity is implemented in a playful (partly gambling) form, which allows students to intellectually and emotionally "liberate themselves", show creative initiative. A business game can be of the following types:

- analysis of specific industrial and professional situations - trainees get acquainted with the situation, with a set of interrelated facts and phenomena characterizing this event. Then the students offer their solutions in a particular situation, which are collectively discussed.

There is a detailed description of this type of work in the linguistic literature (the case study method [5]), but it is carried out not in the form of a game, but in the form of a written analysis followed by discussion. Students are offered a detailed description of real situations borrowed from professional practice in various fields of activity. Having studied the conditions and facts, students should analyze what is the cause of the problem, what positive and negative sides can be found in the very fact of the occurrence of this problem, which facts are the key to its resolution, as well as propose and justify a way(s) to solve the problem.

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- role-playing - students receive initial data on the situation, and then take on the performance of certain roles. For example, behavior in a conflict situation can be played out from the position of an ingratiation, accuser, and under. The roles are performed in the presence of other students, who then evaluate the actions of the participants in the situation, choose the optimal line of behavior in these conditions.

The speech task can be based on differences in the information available to students, in beliefs and worldview attitudes, and so on. In accordance with this, there are games based on differences in pictures (picture gap), in texts (text gap), in beliefs (belief / opinion gap), in evidence (reasoning gap) [6].

The construction of utterances of this type of speech, as a description, is trained in games based on picture gap. For example, two participants in the game are given similar pictures. They have to find the differences based on their descriptions without showing the pictures to each other. Variants of this game are possible: all players receive postcards, and without showing them to each other, but only describing them, they must find pairs of identical postcards (the game "Twins"). The game "Another Age" is also interesting in terms of teaching description techniques: players are invited to imagine themselves younger or older and tell about themselves taking into account these age characteristics.

An example of a belief/opinion gap, when trainees have different beliefs and need to develop a common opinion, can be the game "Optimists and pessimists". The players from the team of optimists make optimistic statements on a given topic, and the pessimists should object to them. Then the teams develop a common point of view.

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